

The Book in Captivity for Eight and Half Centuries

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Annotation: This article, regarding one of the most crucial, valuable, and historical work of turkic literature world, discusses the fate of the book “Devonu Lugotit-Turk” by Mahmood Koshghariy: translations, the time until the book is delivered to readers.

Key words: Mahmood Koshghariy, book, Devonu Lugotit-Turk, morphology, language, turkic, history, traditions, geography.

The book is called “Youssuf of the Books” by scholars due to the reason that its background is very similar to that of Prophet Youssuf. Prophet Youssuf was thrown into the well by his siblings. The book had almost the same fate. As is known, the author of the book is Mahmood Koshghariy. The book is about turkic languages, and contains valuable information regarding history, geography, social state, and finally, the astronomy of Central Asia and China at that time. The years written are 1071–1072. The book includes synonyms to antonyms, the etymology of the words, morphology, and many more windows of the language. In morphology, the book categorises the words into three groups: verbs, nouns, and conjunctions. Containing more than 250 proverbs along with tens of poems, it's a notable book of all time in the Turkish world.

It took years for the book to be revealed to readers, finally in 1914. Writer Ayniy from Antep, whose real name is Badriddin Makhmood, stated that he used “Devonu Lugotit-Turk” in the first volume of his book, “Ikdul-Juman fi-Tarihi Akhluz-Zamon.” He made the readers aware that his book “Shihabi`s History” was based on “Devonu Lugotit-Turk.”

Secretary Chalabi also published his famous book "Kashf uz-Zunnun" with the help of that Devon.

Having bought the book for 33 liras, Ali Amiriyy said: "As the time I saw the book, my heart skipped the beat due to excitement and endless happiness. This is not the book, this is the whole Turkistan, not Turkistan, but the whole world. It's the Youssuf of the books".

The book was popular in the Ottoman Empire and in the Turkish world.

The teacher, Rifat Effendi, worked on the book's restoration, on the lost parts of it.

In 1935-37th, the book was translated by the group guided by Khalid Sayid in Azerbaijan. In 1937, Well-known Uyghur writer Muhammad Ali translated it into his native language. Later, another Uyghur Qutluq Shavqiy brought one copy from Istanbul on his way routed to Mecca. In 1944, Ismail Damollam (another Uyghur) translated the first part of "Devonu Lugotit-Turk." All of the ones, who attempted to keep the book and translate, were murdered.

The next one to translate was Akhmad Ziyoy. As soon as he finished, he was imprisoned for 20 years, though he died earlier due to torture in the prison. In 1960-63th, again, the attempt was ended with murders.

Finally, in 1984, the book was published in 10,000 copies as a book containing three volumes in Urumchi.

Mahmood Koshghariy also referenced his map (which was spherical) of the world in the book. In the map, there were the names of cities, villages, rivers, mountains, lakes and deserts. The map corresponds mainly to the present-day Eastern Hemisphere. The book also carries data regarding fauna and flora, traditions of the 11th century.

German orientalist K. Brockelman translated the work "Devonu Lugotit-Turk" into German in 1928.

"Devonu Lugotit-Turk" was translated into Uzbek for the second time, with important comments and interpretations in 1960-63, and published in 3 volumes in the "Fan" publishing house in Tashkent, as a result of 35 years of work by linguist, doctor of philology, and professor Salih Mutallibov.

Linguist scientist V. I. Belyaev states about "Devonu Lugotit-Turk": "We should give this work an extremely high rating because it is not copied or taken from

books, but based on personal observation of live materials... The information provided by the author... archaeological discoveries prove most of this message".

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